

DEVELOPMENT OF FeCrSi FIBER/ ALUMINUM ALLOY COMPOSITES FABRICATED BY GRAVITY CASTING

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SUMMARY

Molten aluminum alloy (A336.0) was infiltrated to porous FeCrSi fiber preform by gravity casting with 0.4-0.8 MPa, and FeCrSi fiber/ A336.0 aluminum alloy composites were acquired. By controlling the flow of molten alloy in preform with a support of computer simulation, the dense composites with 0-0.7 % in porosity were acquired. As decreasing porosity, fatigue strength at high temperature was improved dramatically.

Keywords: Gravity casting, FeCrSi fiber, Aluminum alloy, Flow control, Mechanical properties, Simulation

INTRODUCTION

Recently, metal matrix composites are used for many industrial applications such as the automobile parts, electrical parts, heat sink and so on. Many MMCs are fabricated by squeeze casting process in order to obtain dense materials without porosity because of good mechanical properties and reliability. Unfortunately, this process cannot fabricate the large size and complex shaped composites, and has low cost performance. Recently, the low-pressure infiltration process is grate watched for fabrication process of MMC [1, 2]. The low-pressure infiltration process is used with 0.1–0.8MPa pressure of molten alloy in order to infiltrate to the porous reinforcement preform. This pressure is usually used for the conventional casting processes such as the gravity casting, sand casting and die-casting. Therefore, we can obtain the large size and complex shaped MMC products by the conventional technique with high cost performance.

In this study, we focused on the gravity casting, because many foundries have been using this process in order to fabricate the aluminum and magnesium alloy products with high performance properties. But, as the wettability between reinforcement and molten alloy are usually low, this process has been not considered for the fabrication process of MMC. However, the threshold pressure for infiltration of molten alloy to porous preform made by ceramics is not so high, theoretically [3]. So that, the low pressure infiltration is possible in principle. The important is laminar flow of molten alloy in preform, and its careful control in order to obtain the dense composites with high performance. FeCrSi metal fiber was used as the reinforcement of aluminum alloy because of good wettability in this study, and the flow control of molten aluminum alloy in porous reinforcement preform was considered by using flow simulation. Then the composites were actually fabricated by gravity casting and check the microstructure and the mechanical properties of the composites.

COMPOSITE FABRICATION

FeCrSi metal fiber was used for the reinforcement of the composites. Chemical composition, diameter and density of this fiber is 75Fe-20Cr-5Si (wt%), 40 μ m and 7.3 Mg/m³, respectively, which is prepared by NHK Spring Co. in Japan. Matrix used was A336.0 aluminum alloy, which composition is Al-13%Si-1.5%Ni- 1.3%Cu -1.3%Mg (mass%). The composites were fabricated by gravity casting with vacuum system. Figure 1 (a) is a schematic diagram of the gravity casting process. A gravity-casting machine usually includes a pressurized mold, a compressor, a vacuum pump and an air vent. The process of low-pressure casting is illustrated in Figure 1(b). In our experiment, after pouring molten aluminum alloy into the mold, a reducing pressure of 0.05 MPa was applied to the air vent part. The purpose of the reducing pressure was to remove the air inside the mold. Then, a pressure of 0.4 MPa was applied to the molten alloy in order to induce infiltration. The pressure acceleration time was 1 sec. The pressure acceleration time is the time needed to reach 0.4 MPa, the maximum plunger pressure.

Figure 1. Schematic drawing of (a) gravity casting process and (b) pressure pattern used in this study.

The flow of a molten alloy through a porous preform can be determined using Darcy's Law under the following conditions: the fluid flow is laminar and the Reynolds number is less than 1. The most important relation describing the behavior of a fluid flow through a porous preform is Darcy's Law. Darcy's equation is expressed as followings, when the porosity, density and viscosity are constant.

$$U = \frac{K}{\mu} - (\nabla P + \rho g) \quad (1)$$

where,

U: Superficial velocity (mm/s)

ρ : Density of molten alloy (kg/mm³)

K: Permeability of fluid low inside the porous system (mm²)

Here, μ is the viscosity, and K/μ is k , which is the coefficient of permeability of porous systems [4]. In casting mechanics, μ is equivalent to the degree of ventilation. If

the gravity is ignored and only one dimension is taken into account, Equation (1) can be converted into Equation (2). Hence, the coefficient of permeability in Equation (3) is given by the relationship between the infiltration length (h) and the infiltration time (t), as follows [5]:

$$V = -\frac{K}{\mu} \frac{\partial P}{\partial h} \quad (2)$$

$$h = \sqrt{-2 \frac{K}{\mu} \Delta P \sqrt{t}} = a\sqrt{t} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{K}{\mu} = \frac{a^2}{2 \Delta P} \quad (4)$$

where, t is the infiltration time (s), h is the infiltration height (mm), ΔP is a constant (the difference between the infiltration pressures (MPa), and a is the velocity obtained from the infiltration length and speed (mm/s).

In order to predict the flow of molten alloy in preform, the finite difference method (FDM) was used in this study. The infiltration behavior was simulated by the combination of EDM analysis and Darcy's law, which simulation software is by hand made by one self [5]. The estimation of the coefficient of permeability is required for predicting the flow of molten alloy in preform. The coefficient of permeability of the preform with a volume fraction of 15% at a temperature 973K, 1023 K, 1073K were estimated as 0.940 mm³-s/kg, 1.037 mm³-s/kg and 1.115 mm³-s/kg, respectively [6]. As increasing temperatures, the coefficient of permeability increased gradually.

A three-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system was used for the analysis of the infiltration flow inside the preform. Simulation and actual experiments was performed by two typical infiltrations such as with and without barrier plate in order to estimate the effect of flow pattern. By using a barrier plate, the infiltration of molten alloy to preform changed from multi directions to two directions. Figure 2 shows the initial conditions and boundary conditions using barrier plate. Under the initial conditions, the pressure applied to the molten alloy by the plunger was 0.4 MPa, and the pressure at the air vent was 0.1 MPa.

Figure 2. Schematic drawing of low pressure casting with barrier plate. Unit in length is given by mm.

ρ (kg_m/mm^3)	2.7×10^{-6}
g (mm/s^2)	9807
ΔP (MPa)	0.3
Void fraction (%)	0.8
K/μ , permeability coefficient ($\text{mm}^2 \cdot \text{s}/\text{kg}_m$)	1.037
Time step (s)	0.0001

Figure 3. Infiltration behaviour of molten aluminium alloy (A336.0) to FeCrSi fiber preform by simulation, and parameter used in simulation.

Figure 3 shows the results of simulation for two direction infiltrations by using barrier plate. Figure 3(a) shows the initial infiltration under the initial conditions. Figures 3(b) shows the unidirectional flow of the molten alloy inside the preform with a barrier plate, unlike the infiltration without a barrier plate. Figure 3(c) shows the end of the molten alloy infiltration inside the preform. The molten alloy reached the air vent at 0.117 sec. The infiltration flow should be laminar inside the preform, because the collision of molten alloy in preform was not observed.

Figure 4 shows the results of computer simulation for the infiltration of molten alloy and the microstructure of the composites fabricated with and without a barrier plate. In the case of infiltration without barrier plate, the molten alloy collided at center of preform. By using barrier plate, the molten alloy did not collide with itself because the flow of the molten alloy was controlled one-dimensionally. Therefore, a barrier plate ensures the unidirectional flow of the molten alloy inside the preform. Consequently, the porosity at center in composites degrade from 3-6% to 0.3-0.7% by controlling the flow of molten alloy because of no collision.

On the other hand, the pressure distribution of molten alloy is not homogeneous in preform even after finishing infiltration. Figure 5 shows the relationship between the pressure distributions inside the preform calculated by FDM and the local porosity in the composite obtained from the experimental results. The purpose of the calculation was to confirm the dependence of the porosity of the composite on the casting pressure. Figure 5(a) shows the pressure distribution in each positions in composites. Pressure of molten alloy decreased as approaching the air vent. Figure 5(b) shows the relationship between the local pressures inside the preform and the porosity. The porosity was estimated by SEM observation. The results show that the porosity decreased as the

pressure inside the preform increased. And, around the air vent, the porosity increased because of low local pressure of molten alloy.

Figure 4. Porosity inside composite observed by optical microscopy;(a) multidirectional infiltration, (b) two directional infiltration.

Figure 5. Relationship between porosity and local pressure inside preform.

Figure. 6. Effect of applied pressure from 0.4MPa to 0.8MPa on porosity.

One of effective method for decreasing the porosity in composites is higher pressure of molten alloy. Figure 6 shows the porosity of the composite produced with a barrier plate under an applied pressure of 0.4-0.8 MPa. The porosity of the composite decreased with increasing applied pressure. Even when the FeCrSi metal-fiber-reinforced aluminum-alloy composite was fabricated under an applied pressure of 0.4 MPa, the applied pressure was not sufficient, because numerous fine pores were observed inside the composite. However, when the applied pressure was 0.8 MPa, there were no pores in the composite; therefore, an applied pressure of 0.8 MPa was sufficient to produce FeCrSi metal-fiber-reinforced aluminum-alloy composites without pores.

MICROSTRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Figure 7 shows the microstructure of composites fabricated by gravity casting with 0.8MPa. FeCrSi metal fibers were distributed uniformly without pores. Pores seem to distinguish completely.

The composites have high tensile strength and fatigue strength at high temperature between 100-350°C compared with monolithic alloy [7]. The tensile strength of the composite at 573 K containing 20-vol% FeCrSi and that of monolithic A366.0 alloy were 150 MPa and 90 MPa, respectively. The tensile strength of the composite was approximately 65% higher at 573K than that of the monolithic alloy. The fatigue strength of the composites with porosity of 3-6% and with porosity of 0% at 573 K were 71.2 MPa and 98.7 MPa, respectively. Therefore, the fatigue strength of the composite with porosity of 0% was approximately 38.5% higher than that of the composite with porosity of 3-6%.

Figure 8 shows the relationship between fatigue strength and porosity at 573K. The composites with 3-4% in porosity have low fatigue strength and 65MPa. As decreasing the porosity under 1 %, the fatigue strength improved dramatically. Fatigue strength of the composites with 0.7% in porosity is about 82 MPa. The fatigue strength was improved to 102 MPa by dispersing pores completely.

Figure 7. Optical micrograph of porosity in composites fabricated by low pressure casting with 0.8MPa.

Figure 8. Relationship between fatigue strength and porosity.

CONCLUSIONS

Molten aluminum alloy (A336.0) was infiltrated to porous FeCrSi fiber preform by gravity casting with 0.4-0.8 MPa, and 20vol% FeCrSi fiber/ A336.0 aluminum alloy composites were acquired. In order to decrease the porosity, the flow control of the molten alloy by using simulation based on Darcy's law and FDM analysis. Simulation and experiments for infiltration was performed by using doughnut shaped product as a case study. Multidirectional infiltration of molten alloy to preform introduced the many pores in composites. By controlling the infiltration direction, the collision of molten alloy in preform vanished and the porosity in composites decreased dramatically. On the other hand, as the local pressure near the air-bents was low, many pores was introduced. As increasing infiltration pressure, the pore was vanished completely at 0.8MPa in pressure. The dense composites have good mechanical properties at high temperature. Especially, as decreasing porosity, fatigue strength at high temperature was improved dramatically.

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